

Online appendix for
Refining analytic approximation based estimation of
mixed multinomial probit models by parameter
selection

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July 1, 2023

Appendix I: A real data case

Brownstone et al. (1996) have carried out a conjoint analysis study of preferences between alternative vehicles. The study surveyed 4654 people in the state of California, each of whom was asked to choose between six alternatives. The alternatives were described by the variables defined in Table 1.

The data is made available by the Journal of Applied Econometrics data archive (McFadden and Train, 2000). A closer look at the values of the variables points to a peculiarity of the data set. With the exception of the first variable *type*, all other variables have the same values for two alternatives each at every choice occasion. Presumably, the influence

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Variable	Definition
<i>type</i>	one of regular car, sport utility vehicle, sportcar, stationwagon, truck, van
<i>fuel</i>	one of gasoline, methanol, compressed natural gas, electric
<i>price</i>	price of vehicle divided by the logarithm of income
<i>range</i>	hundreds of miles vehicle can travel between refuelings/rechargings
<i>acceleration</i>	tens of seconds required to reach 30 mph from stop
<i>speed</i>	highest attainable speed in hundreds of mph
<i>pollution</i>	tailpipe emissions as fraction of those for new gas vehicles
<i>size</i>	one of mini, subcompact, compact, mid-size or large vehicle
<i>space</i>	fraction of luggage space in comparable new gas vehicle
<i>costs</i>	costs per mile of travel in tens of cents
<i>station</i>	fraction of stations that can refuel/recharge vehicle

Table 1: Variable definitions of the conjoint analysis study of preferences between alternative vehicles.

of the vehicle type on the choice decision should thus be investigated. However, this variable will not be considered in the following, which inevitably leads to multicollinearity. In order to circumvent this problem and to take into account the potentially distorting effect of the vehicle type on the choice decision, only three alternatives are considered, and here only those in which there were three regular cars to choose from, one of which was selected. Thus, 2572 choice occasions can be considered.

In order to determine the extent to which the estimation methods described are suitable not only for statistical inference but also for prediction, the estimation will be based on 2000 data points, leaving 572 for evaluation of prediction performance. This ratio is roughly the same as the training and test data splitting ratio used before.

The underlying utility function of the multinomial mixed probit model is given by $u_{qi} = \beta_q^T x_{qi} + \epsilon_{qi}$. In the following, the variables *pollution*, *space*, *price*, *costs*, and *acceleration* are considered for parameter estimation.

A brief explanation on this: at the time of the survey, the state of California suffered from air pollution generated by vehicles. For this reason, it seems reasonable to find out whether

pollution plays a role in the decision for a certain regular car. The *price* and *costs* of a vehicle certainly play an important role in the decision. The amount of *space* a trunk provides can also serve as a proxy for the *size* of a car, avoiding an additional categorical variable. In a country with a speed limit, a vehicle's top *speed* is unlikely to matter much, although *acceleration* may well be decisive. Considering the age of the study and the low percentage of alternative-fueled cars at the time, the variables *fuel* and *station* are not considered.

Table 2 provides the estimation results for the considered model for SJ without parameter selection in each first line for the considered parameters. The estimation results for SJ with parameter selection and cross-validation parameter $c = 5$ are given in each second line.

Mean values of β	Parameter Estimate	Standard Deviation	Confidence Interval (95%)		Interval Length
<i>pollution</i>	0.172	(0.085)	[0.055	0.386]	0.332
	0.145	(0.063)	[0.038	0.271]	0.232
<i>space</i>	1.572	(0.439)	[1.085	2.731]	1.646
	1.194	(0.325)	[0.939	2.287]	1.348
<i>price</i>	-0.181	(0.047)	[-0.304	-0.126]	0.178
	-0.152	(0.038)	[-0.242	-0.108]	0.134
<i>costs</i>	-0.045	(0.014)	[-0.082	-0.029]	0.053
	-0.039	(0.011)	[-0.066	-0.025]	0.042
<i>acceleration</i>	-0.045	(0.017)	[-0.089	-0.021]	0.067
	-0.031	(0.013)	[-0.064	-0.012]	0.052
Variances of β					
<i>pollution</i>	0.184	(0.293)	[0.016	1.121]	1.104
	0.000	(0.145)	[0.000	0.405]	0.405
<i>space</i>	6.093	(6.603)	[1.054	24.222]	23.167
	1.469	(4.110)	[0.013	15.384]	15.371
<i>price</i>	0.041	(0.319)	[0.003	1.589]	1.586
	0.015	(0.175)	[0.001	0.286]	0.286
<i>costs</i>	0.026	(0.028)	[0.014	0.115]	0.101
	0.016	(0.015)	[0.008	0.051]	0.044

	<i>acceleration</i>	0.029	(0.038)	[0.015	0.151]	0.137
		0.014	(0.021)	[0.002	0.066]	0.064
Covariances of β						
	<i>pollution.space</i>	-0.351	(0.626)	[-1.899	0.251]	2.151
		0.000	(0.000)	[0.000	0.000]	0.000
	<i>pollution.price</i>	-0.021	(0.082)	[-0.203	0.147]	0.351
		0.000	(0.000)	[0.000	0.000]	0.000
	<i>space.price</i>	-0.073	(0.429)	[-1.111	0.613]	1.723
		0.081	(0.226)	[-0.516	0.376]	0.892
	<i>pollution.costs</i>	-0.064	(0.073)	[-0.308	-0.009]	0.299
		0.000	(0.035)	[-0.104	0.000]	0.104
	<i>space.costs</i>	0.267	(0.211)	[0.041	0.769]	0.729
		0.154	(0.136)	[-0.084	0.523]	0.607
	<i>price.costs</i>	0.009	(0.047)	[-0.067	0.059]	0.125
		0.009	(0.016)	[-0.023	0.039]	0.063
	<i>pollution.acceleration</i>	-0.071	(0.059)	[-0.233	-0.006]	0.228
		0.000	(0.000)	[0.000	0.000]	0.000
	<i>space.acceleration</i>	0.053	(0.159)	[-0.341	0.321]	0.661
		0.145	(0.129)	[-0.252	0.269]	0.522
	<i>price.acceleration</i>	0.015	(0.058)	[-0.035	0.141]	0.176
		0.008	(0.021)	[-0.019	0.067]	0.086
	<i>costs.acceleration</i>	0.023	(0.016)	[0.009	0.064]	0.055
		0.015	(0.009)	[-0.003	0.033]	0.036
	Mean across parameters	-	(0.482)	-	-	1.743
		-	(0.274)	-	-	1.014
	Computation time	0.21	-	-	-	-
		6.15	-	-	-	-

Table 2: Real data case estimation results for SJ without parameter selection (each first line) and SJ with parameter selection and cross-validation parameter $c = 5$ (each second line), including standard deviations and confidence intervals based on bootstrapping with 1000 replications.

According to the 95%-confidence intervals based on bootstrapping with 1000 replications,

the mean values of β are estimated significantly different from zero for both approaches. The estimated mean effects differ only slightly from each other and, in particular, point in the same direction for each variable included in the model. Environmental awareness does not seem to be pronounced among the decision-makers, which is indicated by the positive direction of the estimated mean effects of the pollution variable. However, there does not seem to be a pronounced preference for high acceleration cars either. The estimated mean effects of the acceleration variable are negative. The other estimated mean values of β point in the expected directions.

The results of the SJ approach without parameter selection suggest that there may be taste variation for all variable coefficients. However, according to the 95%-confidence intervals, there does not seem to be a correlation between all of them. Here no uniform structure can be discerned at first glance. This observation contrasts with the results of the SJ approach with parameter selection, where there may be no taste variation in the effect of the pollution variable. It is also striking that the effect of the pollution variable does not seem to be correlated with the effects of the other variables. However, considering the presumably low environmental awareness of the decision-makers, these systematic results seem plausible.

The goodness of fit of the two estimation methods is about the same. The proportion of decisions correctly described by the model in the training data is 0.435 for SJ without parameter selection and 0.441 for SJ with parameter selection. The same applies to the prediction quality. The proportion of decisions correctly described by the model in the test data is 0.472 for SJ without parameter selection and 0.479 for SJ with parameter selection. However, the parameter selection approach provides significantly smaller standard deviations and hence confidence intervals ($s = 210$, $z = 3.920$, $p\text{-value} = 0.000$) and thus seems to be the more efficient estimator.

References for Appendix I

Brownstone, D., Bunch, D. S., Golob, T. F., and Ren, W. (1996). A transactions choice model for forecasting demand for alternative-fuel vehicles. *Research in Transportation Economics*, 4:87–129.

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